

SECURITY ARCHITECTURE FOR TACTICAL/STRATEGIC INTEROPERABILITY

Mark E. Dark
(410) 859-4717

Richard A. Dean
(301) 688-0293

DIRNSA, V2
9800 Savage Rd.
Ft. Meade, MD 20755-6000

INTRODUCTION

Anyone who has a hand in planning, designing, or using modern communications systems knows that things have changed. The Information Age has arrived with an explosion of distributed users, data bases, computing networks and communications networks. While we expected this to happen, no one knew exactly what form these changes would take. We now find ourselves surrounded by new information formats and media that did not exist ten years ago.

The technology and market forces have influenced the way we view the world of tactical and strategic communications. Our view of secure communications has always seen the strategic world as unique from the mobile platforms of the tactical world. Interoperability of such systems has always been a goal but has never become a reality. This has changed as a result of the Gulf War. In the Gulf War operation, the demand for an interoperable mix of tactical and strategic resources revealed significant weaknesses. Today, with such concepts as Global Grid and Command Control Communications Computers and Intelligence for the Warrior (C4IFTW), it has grown into a requirement where anyone, anyplace, at anytime can talk to anybody. This expanded view of interoperability coupled with the fact that new communication products are introduced every twelve to eighteen months has forced us to look at providing security for the diverse products and networks a new way. This paper describes a high level architectural methodology for developing future Tactical to Strategic interoperability while addressing security concerns.

BACKGROUND

The foundation of this Architecture is based on several organizing principles that are described below and are presented throughout this document.

Black End-to-End - Security integrity is best served by services that are encrypted and authenticated at each terminating device with no intervening red gateways.

Layering - Layering is believed to be fundamental to efficient interoperation of services in a mixed telecommunications environment. The International Standards Organization (ISO) Open System Interconnect (OSI) model is used here although it does not strictly apply in all cases.

Phasing - A phased solution is essential to an effective and practical solution. A Transitional Architecture is presented which addresses the base of installed equipment and a Future Architecture is presented which accomplishes longer term objectives.

Digitally Based - This scheme recognizes the advantages and the reality inherent in the broad based migration which is occurring from the analog-based to the digital-based telecommunications infrastructure. All solutions point toward that ultimate reality.

Wired and Wireless Service - Future digital networks will support a mixture of services. Wireline connections will offer high speed user data rates of 56 kbps and higher while wireless connections will be limited to user data rates typically less than 8 kbps and as little as 2.4 kbps.

Common Modes - Secure terminals will support multiple modes in order to support interoperability of mixed terminal families in a mixed telecommunications environment. Common Modes will be arrived at by a capabilities exchange. Common modes do not require common terminal equipment. Any approach to interoperability which depends on common physical hardware is doomed to failure.

Interoperable Signaling - Secure interoperable terminals will support a Top Level Signaling Plan which identifies diverse classes of equipment, enables a capabilities exchange, and engages an appropriate secure signaling scheme. The Security Association Management Protocol (SAMP) is a candidate for such a scheme.

Common Voice and Data - The solutions presented here presume a migration toward an integrated voice and data solution. This applies both to the telecommunications infrastructure and the secure services it supports. The Future Architecture presented here presumes a rich mixture of wideband and narrowband secure applications. A Future Narrow Band Digital Terminal (FNBDT) is defined as a least common denominator for interoperability and has these general properties:

- Operates at user data rates of 2.4 and/or 4.8 kbps for use on future narrowband wireless connections using synchronous, transparent asynchronous, or packet bearer services.
- Supports high quality secure voice.
- Supports low speed data services such as E mail, voice mail, imaging(Fax) and data terminals.
- Includes key management, encryption and authentication features necessary for future multi-level security with mixed voice and data applications.
- Supports point to point, broadcast and conference capabilities.

These organizing principles have created a new "business philosophy" which forces security development to comply with commercial vendor development processes and schedules. The overall goals of this philosophy being to provide interoperable, upgradeable and transparent security services. By applying the above principles, a security architecture has been developed which supports

tactical to strategic interoperability that is independent of the media which the secure communications will traverse. The realization of this architecture methodology and new "business philosophy" coupled with innovative commercial technology will provide a wider range of interoperable security services and products for the war fighter.

BASIC PROPERTIES

Layered Approach - Fundamental to this Architecture is the approach of using a layered model to accomplish compatible connections. It is important to separate the many attributes one normally sees with a terminal equipment from the many potentially independent functions that are accomplished. A system such as STU-III integrates these many functions into a single application service. Interoperability of different families of equipments can only be accomplished by factoring these functions into distinct categories where compatible functions such as network connection, encryption scheme, key management, etc. can be resolved for different devices. One such technique for factoring systems functions is the ISO layering concept which organizes telecommunications services into seven distinct hierarchical layers to define interoperable service. This same approach can be used for INFOSEC services except that these layers must be augmented to include the additional functions such as keying, authentication and encryption. Interoperation can occur when peer entities are created directly or indirectly by translation or interworking.

A concept for layered interoperability can be seen in Figure 1 which shows interoperation between a STU-IIIID connected to a Digital Network and a STU-III on the PSTN. STU-IIIID results from organizing the functions of the STU-III terminal into layers as shown in Figure 1. The transport layer and above represent the STU-IIIID functions and allows a standard digital representation for STU-III interoperability. Interoperability is accomplished by agreement on peer compatibility at the transport layer and above for the function to be accomplished. By defining interoperability to be accomplished at the transport layer and above, all other applications can be translated to this reference point and translated into suitable formats for compatible operation. Here the functions associated with voice coding, encryption, keying, and authentication are

mapped into ISO layers. At each layer of the model, there is peer compatibility. Below the transport layer, the link and physical layer protocols, such as the modems defined in FSVS 220 or the TDMA air interface defined by TIA Std IS54 (Digital Cellular), can be reflected to accommodate the particular requirements of the network. Transitioning across networks can be accomplished by interworking functions suited to the individual networks. In the case of the PSTN to Digital Cellular connection shown, the network interworking is transparent while the link and physical layers require a conversion from the FSVS modem format to the IS54 digital format. Other examples can be used to show the required interworking and where it occurs in the system.

The layering of STU-III in Figure 1 highlights the fundamental organization of this architecture. By separating the functions included in the transport layer 4 and above which are determined by the terminal from the functions of the network layer 3 and below which are determined by the media, the terminal functionality can become media independent. It supports a potentially common black digital network or media interface and allows gateways or interworking to be black. Isolation of the terminal functions from the media means that common interoperable secure voice and data applications can be achieved across a broad spectrum of media. This would include most PSTN, Land Mobile, Cellular, and Satellite systems in the strategic and tactical world. It could also apply to more exotic media such as ECCM and covert spread spectrum applications.

GENERAL ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION

A general description of the Interoperable Voice Architecture is provided below. The architecture follows from a connection concept presented in Figures 2 and 3 which show a Transitional Architecture and a Future Architecture. These include many different networks and connection options and equipment configurations for the STU-III, STE, LMR, the FNBDT and Tactical Systems.

TRANSITIONAL ARCHITECTURE

In the Transition Architecture shown in Figure 2, interoperability is accomplished by supporting peer level interoperability from the physical layer up through the

application layer. In this case, the physical layer is assumed to be analog with the link layers assumed to be FVSV 220 compatible modems. This reflects the current dominance of analog wired and wireless networks. Where systems in the Transitional Architecture do not support analog modems, as in the case of digital mobile connections, interworking functions are incorporated to create compatible peer functions. Transitional interoperability is accomplished by supporting STU-III capabilities directly or indirectly. STU-III was selected for this role because it represents today's de facto standard for strategic secure voice. Its widespread availability and low data rate allow it to be adapted to most network applications either directly in the case of wireline or FM radio, or indirectly using an interworking function. In addition, STU-III connections can support a basic set of voice band data applications including FAX, E-Mail and Computer Terminal Emulation. A digital variation of STU-III, identified as STU-III D, provides a transport layer compatible standard whereby STU-III compatibility can be extended to a variety of mobile networks and Tactical Systems. In this architecture the STU-III D can be used directly or as an overlay of functions on other terminals such as the LMR, MSE or STE terminals as shown in Figure 2. This Transition Architecture follows the organizing principles presented above where possible. The features associated with this approach are described in the paragraphs below.

Analog Interoperability - The Transitional Architecture depends on creating interoperability among STU-III, STE, LMR and Tactical Systems by enabling analog connections from end to end which will support FSVS synchronous data modems at a minimum rate of 2.4 kbps. This can be accomplished directly for terminals connected to analog networks or indirectly for terminals connected to narrowband digital networks using Interworking Functions. It can also be accomplished, if necessary, from a Red Enclave with a tandem connection via a STU-III. While such connections deviate from the organizing principles, unique requirements may dictate the need for tandem or gateway operation.

Common Modes - Interoperability is accomplished by defining a common set of functions within this architecture that will be incorporated within different families of equipments and constitute a complete protocol for interoperable secure voice. In general, the common interoperable mode will be fixed and defined for all terminals for any given time. The common interoperable

mode for the Transition Voice Architecture is the STU-III protocol defined in FSVS 210 and 220, and the STU-IIID.

Transition Signaling - In the Transition Architecture, STU-III signaling will be used. Where multifunctional terminals include STU-III as a sub-mode of operation, recognition of STU-III go-secure tones will be performed to initiate a compatible signaling scheme.

Layered Interoperability - The interoperable mode will support peer compatibility from Layer 1 (Physical) to Layer 7 (Application) as illustrated in Figure 1.

Mode Negotiation - Mode negotiation is accomplished by identification of STU-III Go Secure messages and associated signaling within the FSVS 210.

FUTURE ARCHITECTURE

Interoperability for future INFOSEC systems will be accomplished by creating peer compatibility at the transport layer and above of the ISO model on end-to-end digital connections using a subset of common functions defined as the Future Narrow Band Digital Voice Terminal (FNBDT) interoperable mode. All other terminal interoperability will be accomplished by interworking or translation to that layer. Figure 3 shows a variety of such connections. These include the many possible configurations of FNBDT, STE, LMR and Tactical Systems over the Defense Information System Network (DISN), digital mobile networks and some tactical networks. The STU-III connected to the PSTN is shown here operating through a gateway. Backward compatible Black end-to-end interoperation with STU-III can be accomplished as an optional feature of terminals in the Future Architecture. Other connections will require Red tandem operation. These terminal descriptions and network capabilities are described in later paragraphs. The following general functions shown in this architecture must be accomplished for secure interoperable voice:

End-to-End Digital Connectivity - Inherent in the voice connections between these FNBDT, STE, and LMR equipments is the ability for all terminals to establish connections that support end-to-end digital synchronous or transparent (no flow control) asynchronous service, support bit count integrity, and support a minimum rate of 2.4 kbps. Data connections can include other end-to-end bearer services such as X.25 packet service.

Common Modes - Interoperability is accomplished by defining a common subset of functions within this architecture that will constitute a complete protocol for interoperable secure voice and will be incorporated within different families of equipments. This common mode is extracted from a menu exchange between terminal equipments after a digital connection has been established. In general, the common interoperable mode will be fixed and defined for all terminals for any given time. However, the menu structure is defined so as to allow an evolution of the common mode with changes in technology or policy. The common mode in the Future Architecture is the FNBDT.

Transport Layer Interoperable - The reference layer for which interoperable connections are defined is the data stream that appears on the RS232 connection of a Data Communications Equipment (DCE) port (i.e., a modem or an I.430 ISDN connection). The transport layer and every layer above will require a peer layer equivalence for each interoperable device in the architecture. The transport layer and above protocol for this generation of the architecture is the yet to be defined FNBDT protocol. The layers below the network layer will depend on the network on which the interoperable equipment is connected. The transport layer and above protocols can be reflected onto many different networks via physical protocols such as analog modems for PSTN operation, the IS54 protocol for Digital Cellular, or V.110 or V.120 for ISDN. In the various applications, Interworking Function modems and rate adaptors are used to translate, where necessary, the protocol across networks.

Mode Negotiation - Inherent in the ability for different families of INFOSEC equipments to interoperate is a negotiation by the terminal equipments of a common set of protocols and functions under which the secure traffic will be conducted. Mode negotiation will require maintenance of a functional menu by each terminal equipment as well as a Top Level Signaling Plan or SAMP to complete the negotiation.

Functional Menu - The mode negotiation will be accomplished by exchanging functional menus of the terminal devices. Menus will represent all of the capabilities of the terminal equipment that would affect connection options. In general, this Functional Menu could enable interoperability in a number of modes that were available at both terminal equipments. However, as part of standardizing interoperability, a set of default

features will be installed on future terminals and selected when dissimilar devices are connected. An example of a default set of terminal features would be those associated with the FNBDT which is the default for the future generation of interoperation. Future generation interoperability may evolve with new default features for interoperability. This might, for example, result from a migration to a new mainstream technology or toward a new preferred encryption algorithm. Future generation equipments may include earlier default functionality so as to maintain backward compatibility. In addition, a terminal's functional menu might include a preference for some features such as voice algorithm and connection option. Mechanisms for exchanging functional menus and resolving connection modes will be accomplished by a Top Level Signaling Scheme or SAMP.

Top Level Signaling Plan - When different equipment families or classes are connected across various network configurations, interoperability can be accomplished using common interoperable modes using Functional Menus and the Top Level Signaling Plan. The purpose of this plan is to get the connected terminals into a common interoperable protocol. A simplified state diagram of the operation of this plan is shown in Figure 4.

All future interoperable Secure Voice equipments will begin the protocol by establishing a digital end-to-end connection from which the interoperable protocol can begin. The nature of the network connection may be established from user information provided by the network signaling channel or by terminal access limitations. Secure operation on this defined connection can then proceed by initiation of either a same-class go secure request or an interoperable go secure request. If the interoperable Go Secure Request is initiated, the terminal will initiate a Mode Exchange operation. If the exchange identifies a same class equipment, that protocol will be initiated. Otherwise, a common mode of operation will be attempted by the exchange of menus. When a common interoperable mode is identified, that protocol will be initiated. If no interoperable modes are identified then an abort message is sent. This confirms to both users that a connection has been established but no interoperable modes are available. The top level signaling associated with this scheme is shown in Figure 4. A simple series of message exchanges enables the initiation of a functional menu exchange followed by selection of a common mode and an interoperable protocol.

Security Association Management Protocol - One mechanism for accomplishing the Top Level Signaling Plan is the SAMP which is now planned for use in the STE and is in development by the IEEE committee 802.10. This scheme shows promise as the connecting thread to support interoperable signaling at the application level for all future voice and data terminals.

CONNECTED NETWORKS

The Transition and Future Architectures are intended to connect different classes of secure voice equipment operating over different networks. This is shown in the connection diagrams in Figures 2 & 3 and is a natural reflection of the diversity of telecommunications networks and services that will appear in this decade. The architectures are created around the Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN). The PSTN is an abstraction for a multitude of national and international carrier networks that offer a variety of end-to-end services. Figure 3 shows the DISN at the core of the architecture which in reality will be services which are supported by most carriers. The nature of digital service will vary by region and over time and is intended to include enhancements such as SONET and ATM. For example, early implementations of ISDN will be built upon T1 service. Likewise, ISDN service in Europe may vary from North American service. This architecture assumes that these differences can and will be resolved within the networks to support a transparent service. It also assumes that future terminals will reflect national and international standards so as to enable end-to-end digital connections.

The Transition Architecture in Figure 2 also shows PSTN analog service as a separate network. This is also an abstraction as analog service is integral to virtually all PSTN networks. However, this representation reflects a class of users supported by various carriers or at remote locations where digital end-to-end service is not available. This class of user is primarily supported by STU-III and requires a modem for end-to-end digital service. Today, this class of service is the norm with STU-III operation. In the future, only a sma¹ class of users will require this service. It should be recognized, however, that some form of this service will likely be required for the foreseeable future as analog end-to-end service requires the least complexity and is the interoperable mode of last resort when

network digital interoperability is unavailable. All PSTN analog connections to the digital networks require an Interworking Function (IWF) for interoperation. This consists primarily of a compatible modem and associated control for configuring this within the network.

The Interoperable Voice Architecture connections in Figures 2 & 3 also show future mobile digital systems connected with the other networks. Most mobile networks are extensions of the PSTN and operate through the PSTN to make a connection to a non-mobile user. The digital mobile networks are shown explicitly as the Digital Cellular Telephone, Digital Satellite and Land Mobile Radio connections. While each of these serves a different user community and has different link protocols, they each are constrained by low data rate RF channels. Each of these systems will require an Interworking Function modem (IWF_m) for operation with STU-III for the Transition Architecture and in the Future Architecture each will require a Interworking Function rate adaption (IWF_{ra}) for interoperation with high speed digital networks. Schemes for multimedia wireless access which are consistent with this architecture are in development and described in Ref. 3. The detailed nature of these functions is not as yet defined by standards and will require special attention if interoperation is to be achieved.

The Transition Architecture in Figure 2 also shows a limited Military Tactical connection through the PSTN Network. This connection assumes that a suitable interface and a modem interworking function can be established with the TRI-TAC/MSE switch. This connection will enable black end-to-end service across these networks and provide interoperable service. This assumes that a STU-III tactical terminal can be integrated into a TRI-TAC Switch. In the Future Architecture, the TRI-TAC switch is assumed to be replaced with a Tactical DISN which is supported by STE terminals and FNBDT. The Tactical world reflects the standard wired and wireless infrastructure in the commercial world. In this case, Tactical-Strategic interoperability is greatly enhanced with a large integrated set of common voice and data services.

Finally, the architecture includes connections with military digital radio systems. These systems could include conventional HF and SATCOM digital radio systems. In the Transition Architecture, a suitable modem interworking function would be required to support this

interoperable connection between a STU-III and other compatible connections on the network. Military Radio systems have features that resemble commercial wireless networks as they relate to interoperable secure voice except that they are typically switched through a Radio Wireline Interface for access to the PSTN. For the Future Architecture, all-digital connections are expected from Tactical/Mobile networks through the commercial digital infrastructure using FNBDT common modes.

CONNECTED TERMINALS

The Transition and Future Architecture connection diagrams shown in Figures 2 & 3 show connections between classes of secure voice products that include the STU-III, FNBDT, LMR and STE families of equipments. These diagrams emphasize the interoperable connections across different networks and with different terminal equipments. It does not show the variety of same-class operation that will likely represent much of the overall traffic. This section identifies the configurations of the different secure voice terminals shown in Figure 3 and describes the functions included in each.

STU-III and FNBDT Terminals - Many configurations of STU-III are fielded and others are in development. All STU-III's have a minimum set of interoperable capabilities for operation on the analog PSTN. These include the FSVS 210/220 signaling plan with full and half-duplex modems, Firefly keying and authentication, Saville encryption and Fed Std 1015 LPC voice encoding. Many contractor proprietary enhancements are available on some units, and current generation units offer interoperable Fed Std 1016 CELP voice encoding. From the perspective of this architecture, however, only the interoperable features of the STU-III will be considered.

The most significant features of the STU-III are that it is an analog modem-based terminal functionally integrated into a single package and cannot be modified for the purposes of future interoperability. It was not developed with future digital networks in mind. Its use is so pervasive, however, it is expected to be a major component of secure voice interoperation for several years. As such, interoperability for the near future will be built around accommodation of the basic interoperable modes

of STU-III. This can be accomplished by adding a STU-III interoperable mode within new equipments and by surrounding the STU-III with interworking devices that will support its continued operation.

Newer variations of STU-III will offer opportunities to enhance and simplify interoperation. The STU-IIIID specification was defined in an effort to partition the functions of STU-III in such a way that a digital end-to-end connection might be accomplished for operation in digital networks like Mobile Systems and ISDN. STU-IIIID represents a reflection of the FSVS 220 signaling onto the digital transport layer of the ISO model. This configuration of STU-III will enable development of new equipments such as a hand-held Digital Cellular STU-III. New variations of STU-III should incorporate, in addition to standard interoperable modes, an option for a digital RS-232 port that supports the STU-IIIID functionality. Variations of STU-IIIID appear in the Transition Architecture on multiple networks and applications. STU-IIIID can appear on any digital network and interoperate with a like protocol device. It can work through Digital Cellular, Digital Satellite, Military Radios, and LMR via an analog (modem) Interworking Function to talk to analog STU-III's on PSTN.

After a transition period, the operation of STU-III will be limited to those terminals that support the STU-III protocols and operate on analog networks. Interoperation of STU-III with devices based on the Future Architecture will require gateways for service. This can be accomplished by modem interworking for future devices that are backward compatible. Eventually, a red gateway may be the only interoperable mechanism.

The FNBDT will follow the STU-III as the common interoperable terminal. This may be a new class of narrow band terminal or may simply be a subset of features found in a broad class of equipments that support interoperable voice and data services.

Dual Mode STE Terminals - STE Terminals are a new secure product family that are designed specifically for operation on multi-media connections which are planned to include analog, ISDN, ATM, and TRI-TAC/MSE networks/systems. This equipment class will offer a variety of new services for data, video, and voice applica-

tions. The STE class of equipment will offer interoperability with a dual mode terminal which has voice interoperability consistent with the Transition and Future Architectures.

The STE terminals are shown in Figures 2 & 3 as supporting both the ISDN and either STU-III analog or FNBDT functionality. In the Transition Architecture, this may be accomplished directly with a physical connection to a STU-III equipment, incorporation of a STU-III subassembly, or integration of the STU-III functions within multipurpose programmable components. Physically connected STU-III connections might also be multiplexed as in a red switch configuration subject to certification. STE terminals in the Future Architecture will most likely incorporate FNBDT functions with other STE functions.

All STE terminals will implement SAMP to support mode negotiation. For the Transition Architecture, STE equipments will be equipped with an analog STU-III compatible mode. For the Future Architecture, STE terminals must incorporate rate adaption via a standard technique common to interoperable equipments with FNBDT-equipped devices.

Land Mobile Radio Terminals - LMR terminals are a new generation of mobile secure voice equipments intended for digital operation over VHF and UHF mobile radio channels. This class of terminal will offer primarily mobile voice communications keyed with Net Variables. Operation into the PSTN will occur with more frequency in future LMR applications as Trunked Radio systems are used to manage LMR channels. Trunked Radio standards include options for PSTN connections. Interworking Functions incorporated within these interfaces will enable digital connections across the LMR-PSTN boundary.

LMR equipments may be configured to support this Interoperable Voice Architecture. For the Transition Architecture, these terminals will require incorporation of STU-IIIID functionality. This can be accomplished directly with an RS-232 connection to a STU-IIIID device, with an optional subassembly or by integration into programmable multipurpose modules. This will be accompanied by a STU-III compatible Interworking Function at the Trunk Radio/PSTN interface. For the Future Architecture,

interoperable LMR terminals will incorporate the FNBDT functions and will interoperate through the Trunked Radio/DISN interface with a standard rate adaption Interworking Function.

LMR terminals must incorporate functions necessary to enable a data mode that connects with the LMR Trunked Radio Interworking Function. It must also include the Top Level Signaling Plan that will enable interoperable mode negotiation.

PROGRESS TO DATE

Secure Terminal Equipment - The STE effort will meet the requirements of both commercial and Government by bridging the gap between the current 280,000 analog STU-III units and the all-digital STE of the future. The STE will implement the High Grade Programmable Large Scale Integration Chip for cryptography and will include a PCMCIA crypto ignition card. The STE specifications for signalling plans and interoperable modes are nearing completion.

TRI-TAC/MSE - The TRI-TAC/MSE program is integrating digital STU-III technology in the tactical battlefield environment to meet the C4FTW requirements in the Transition Architecture. The program will integrate Digital Non-Secure Voice Terminal signalling in a STU-III platform to allow access to tactical switches. A demonstration of this capability is scheduled for later this year at the Joint Warrior Interoperability Demonstrations (JWID'94).

Commercial Wireless - The commercial wireless efforts will implement a growing commercial, worldwide terrestrial and satellite infrastructure with connections into the PSTN. STU-III interoperability with commercial wireless is being factored into the emerging standards. Specific programs include efforts to use these emerging networks to replace and complement current Land Mobile Radio networks and infrastructures. The development of a small digital STU-III is being considered to secure these networks and systems as part of the Transition Architecture.

Satellite - Current efforts involve the integration of 2.4 kbps STU-III terminal and a STU-III FSVS 220 reverse modem with a small brief-case INMARSAT-M terminal. The integration of these capabilities will provide

users with worldwide digital secure voice, fax, and data services over the INMARSAT-M system. Secure INMARSAT-M service was scheduled to begin 1 February, 1994.

STU-III - The STU-III Black Digital Interface Specification (FSVS 211) is in the review and coordination process for formal publication. The FSVS 211 document specifies an RS-232 interface and a digital signal protocol which provides a mechanism for STU-III functionality to operate over digital networks and systems.

MINTERM - A Proof-of-Concept effort is under development which will integrate STU-III capability into the KY-99 MINTERM tactical platform and implement a radio wireline interface using COTS hardware and semi-custom software. This added capability in the KY-99 provides a way to meet the C4FTW Combat Net Radio (HF/VHF/UHF) requirements in the Transition Architecture. A demonstration of this capability is scheduled for later this year at JWID'94.

2.4 kbps Vocoder Development - The objective of the 2.4 kbps vocoder development is to have a voice quality at least equal to or better than the 4.8 kbps FED-STD 1016 CELP. Results of initial testing and analysis by the DoD Speech Consortium in 1993 indicates a high probability of achieving this goal. A second review of vocoder candidates will be later this summer with a final review scheduled for late 1995.

SAMP Development - Several security initiatives with in the Government are currently planning to implement SAMP. A coordinated effort is underway to ensure that a unified SAMP solution evolves to facilitate Interoperability between the programs and to coordinate the Governments efforts with the development of the 802.10 standards work.

REFERENCES

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3. "Transparent Data Service with Multiple Wireless Access", R.A. Dean, A.L. Levesque, International Mobile Satellite Conference, Pasadena, CA, June 1993.

Figure 1: Layered STU-III Connection to TDMA Cellular

Figure 2: Transition Interoperable Voice Architecture Connections

Figure 3: Future Architecture Connections

Figure 4: Top Level Signalling Scheme for Mode Negotiation